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RESTORATION OF THE LIBERATED LANDS OF AZERBAIJAN THROUGH INNOVATIVE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The article illustrates the scope of the destruction and damage caused by Armenia's military aggression against Azerbaijan, including cultural heritage destruction and environmental terror. Also, the liberated areas' mineral, raw material, energy, and water resources, as well as tourism opportunities, are depicted. The characteristics of these regions' primary economic development directions are given. The article also points out that for the economy to continue to develop in liberated areas, more efficient use of available material, financial, and labor resources, natural resources, and scientific and technological advances must be ensured. The liberated territories are rich in natural resources, and specific measures for the formation and development of complex innovative infrastructures and entrepreneurship in these territories can provide opportunities for the effective use of these resources, thereby increasing the speed of our country's economic development. The development of logistics can also establish additional profit and speed up the improvement of the region. In this regard, the article provides appropriate proposals and recommendations for the development of the economy in the freed territories.

Keywords: liberated territories, natural resources, infrastructure, entrepreneurship, innovation, directions of development, state program.

During the occupation of the regions of Azerbaijan, i.e. Fizuli, Jabrayil, Zangilan, Gubadli, Lachin, Kalbajar, Aghdam and other settlements of Karabagh, almost everything was ruined and hectares of forest were destroyed by the Republic of Armenia. All of them were destroyed by Armenia during the occupation, not during the First Karabakh War. Furthermore, during the occupation, the Republic of Armenia had been using most of the richest mineral deposits, such as 5 gold deposits, 6 mercury deposits, 2 copper deposits, 1 lead-zinc deposit, 19 facing stones deposits, 10 sawn stones deposits, 4 cement raw materials deposits, 13 different types of building stones deposits, 1 soda raw material deposit, 21 pumice and volcanic ash deposits, 10 clay deposits, 9 sand-gravel deposits, 5 building sand deposits, 9 gypsum anhydride, and gypsum deposits, 1 perlite deposit, 1 obsidian deposit, 3 vermiculite, and 14 colored and ornamental stone deposits, as well as 11 fresh underground water deposits and 10 mineral water deposits [3] in Azerbaijan illegally and without the permission of Azerbaijan.

It is appropriate to note that before the occupation, Karabakh provided around 15% of the total amount of wheat in Azerbaijan. The share of viticulture products in these territories reached 32%. Karabakh and Eastern Zangezur provided 15% of all meat products, more than 17% of milk, 20% of wool and 4.0% of eggs in the country. In addition, more than 15% of cattle and 19% of small cattle accounted for these areas. In Lachin, Aghdam, Fuzuli, Jabrayil, and Kalbejar regions, livestock played a dominant role in agriculture and formed a significant part of the local budget.

Also, in other regions of Karabakh there were livestock farms. Before the occupation, 17 industrial enterprises functioned in Aghdam, including a machine-tool plant, grain and meat processing plants, a carpet weaving factory, a tractor repair plant, and many others. All of them were destroyed by the invaders [2].

It should be noted that the restoration of the liberated territories of Azerbaijan is included in the "Azerbaijan 2030: National Priorities for Socio-Economic Development" (approved by the decree of President Ilham Aliyev dated February 2, 2021) [6]. The identification of this issue as one of the five national priorities for the socio-economic development of the country confirms that the government of Azerbaijan attaches great importance to it.

Literature Review: Doctor of Economics, Professor Nazim Muzaffarli and Eldar Ismailov published the first fundamental work, "Restoration of post-conflict areas of Azerbaijan: conceptual fundamentals" in 2010, dedicated to the restoration of infrastructure, resettlement, normal living, and job creation in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan. Doctor of Economics, Professor Tarbiz Aliyev's articles "Directions for the Development of Entrepreneurship in the Liberated Territories of Azerbaijan based on progressive forms of management" (Aliyev T., 2021) and "Restoring the Economy of Karabakh And Eastern Zangesur on the Basis of Sustainable and Inclusive Development Concepts" (Aliyev T., 2022) are also deserve high praise in terms of the formation and development of entrepreneurship in the liberated territories. Doctor of Philosophy in economics Ramil Aliyev and senior research fellow Sevda Makhmudova proposed some suggestion [1] regarding the development of entrepreneurship in liberated lands in their article named "Directions of entrepreneurship development in the territories liberated from occupation" published in 2021.

Research methods: Statistical analysis, a systematic approach, forecasting, and the formulation of a set of measures to improve the economy throughout the liberated territories. In the 1990s, the Republic of Armenia occupied 20 percent of Azerbaijan's territory, and as a result, about one million Azerbaijanis became refugees and displaced persons. These people have been the victims of the ethnic cleansing and genocide policies of the Republic of Armenia. They have been deprived of their basic human rights. With the help of foreign patrons, Armenia managed to keep the occupied Azerbaijani territories under its control for nearly 30 years. Azerbaijan has demonstrated humanism by preferring the peaceful liberation of occupied lands in accordance with international law. However, for 27 years, the resolution of the UN Security Council was not implemented by Armenia, and the OSCE Minsk Group was unable to contribute to the resolution of the Karabakh conflict in a peaceful way. At the same time during the occupation period of the territory of Azerbaijan, 23 000 Armenians were illegally resettled from Armenia, Lebanon and other countries of the world, including: 8 500 people to Nagorno-Karabakh, 13 000 people to Lachin, 700 people to Kalbajari, 520 people to Zangilan, 280 people to Jabrayil [2]. Moreover, as a result of Armenia's aggression, over twenty thousand Azerbaijani people were killed, and over fifty thousand were injured or disabled. Furthermore, more than 900 settlements have been plundered, and destroyed; more than 6 000 industrial and agricultural enterprises have been destroyed and plundered; over 150 000 residential buildings (over 9 000 000 square meters of living space); 4 366 social and cultural facilities; and 695 medical centers and institutions have been ruined. As a result of the occupation, the agricultural lands, water industry, hydro-technical equipment, transportation, and communication lines were totally destroyed. In the occupied territories of Azerbaijan, 927 libraries, 464 historical monuments and museums, over 100 archeological monuments, 6 theatres and concert halls have been totally destroyed and plundered. More than 40 000 precious articles and exhibits have been robbed from plundered museums [8]. The working group, specializing in the situation in conflict countries, estimated the damage from the occupation of 20% of the territories of Azerbaijan by Armenia in the amount of about 820 billion dollars [2].

Azerbaijan's attempts to resolve the conflict peacefully failed due to Armenia's intention to expand the occupied territories, which forced Azerbaijan to resolve the conflict by military-

political means in full compliance with international law, the UN Charter, and the principles of the OSCE. Relying on the full and unanimous support of the Azerbaijani people, state, and all political forces, the heroic Azerbaijani soldiers and officers managed to liberate the occupied lands from the enemy and ensure the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan in just 44 days. One of the most important problems facing the government now is restoring the territories destroyed by Armenian vandals and returning our displaced citizens to their homeland. It is noteworthy that this work has already begun, and for this purpose in 2021, the government initially allocated 2.2 billion Azerbaijani manats [7]. It is assumed that the government of Azerbaijan will achieve the restoration of the territories destroyed by Armenian vandals in a short period of time, and internally displaced people (IDP) will return to their native lands. One of the main issues is to provide employment for the able-bodied population resettled in these areas. Therefore, I believe that the resettlement of IDPs in the liberated territories should be carried out in parallel with the creation of appropriate work places in those areas.

Professor Nazim Muzaffarli and Eldar Ismailov noted ("Restoration of post-conflict areas of Azerbaijan: conceptual fundamentals", 2010) that due to the restoration of liberated areas, there will be a number of recovery priorities that can be considered common to all the liberated areas. The relative importance of these priorities varies, and each stage of the post-conflict recovery process will have its own set of tasks. Today, those stages look like the followings: preparation stage; initial recovery phase; the main recovery phase; repatriation phase; adaptation phase. Of course, these stages are only conceptual and therefore conditional in a sense [5].

At present, construction and restoration works are underway in the liberated territories, infrastructure areas are being created, several power substations and an international airport in Fizuli have been put into operation. Also, practical cooperation has already begun with foreign companies in the field of construction work in Karabakh. Thus, in order to create electricity infrastructure in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan, a supply agreement was signed between Azerenergy and the company Ansaldo Energia (Italian) in the field of mutual cooperation. According to the agreement, the Italian company will equip four units with 110-kilovolt substations that will be built in the districts of Agdam, Fizuli, Kalbajar, and Gubadli. According to the Memorandum on Cultural and Scientific Cooperation signed between the GOSB Technopark, which supports 130 technology companies in Turkey, and the Azerbaijan Innovation Agency, a High Technology Park will be created in Karabakh. The High Technology Park is planned to conduct the latest "soft" and "hard" scientific research, as well as implement the production of high-tech devices [4].

Suggestions and proposals: Economic development in the liberated areas has to be based on the effective use of knowledge and information, which leads to the development of innovative economic growth. For this purpose, State programs for the restoration of Azerbaijan's liberated territories should be developed in a way that allows proper budgetary control and efficient use of budgetary allocations in order to achieve the creation of knowledge-intensive industries with quality assurance and a boost in national production's competitiveness.

In order to increase foreign and domestic investment in innovation and the implementation of joint scientific, technical, and innovation activities in the liberated territories, the state has to create a favorable business environment in this area. In the first stage, to handle financial challenges in the sphere of innovation and attract domestic and foreign investors, depreciation and tax legislation must be upgraded. Entrepreneurs want to make more profit while working when they adopt new ideas. In this sense, income tax rates should be set in a way that encourages entrepreneurship, particularly innovative entrepreneurship, and expands

the number of entrepreneurs interested in this area. This instrument is critical in promoting innovative entrepreneurship in industrialized countries, and as a result, each country is searching for a better profit taxation model. For example, in most industrialized countries, discounts apply in the income tax system for research and development. In the second stage, it is important to create and improve legislation that affects innovation policy. A market infrastructure, including a central information system within the country, must be created in the third stage. In the innovation process cycle, which encompasses research, processing, production preparation, production, and sales, information plays an important role. In the fourth stage, it is necessary to establish financial institutions that support innovation and to form a legislative framework in this area. One of most significant institutional gaps in the Republic of Azerbaijan's financial system is the absence of institutions (business angels and venture capital) that provide early financing in the country. To address this gap, the following purposeful economic and political measures should be taken in the following areas:

- Expanding state support for the initial commercialization of innovation projects.
- Ensuring the establishment and development of specialized financial institutions for the initial financing phase of newly established small and medium-sized innovation firms.
- Government support for the establishment of new financial structural units of the state as state support for R&D and innovation, as well as the establishment of appropriate private financial institutions (business angels, venture capital firms).
- Improvement the banking system.

Priority areas for the development of the economy in the liberated territories. The liberated territories have considerable potential for the establishment and development of business structures, including both production and services. However, in my opinion, in order to create innovative business structures that will operate in both the production and service spheres, the priority areas should be identified by taking into account the available natural resources, opportunities, and local characteristics.

In my point of view the following priorities have to be ensured innovatively: construction material production in the districts of Fuzuli, Jabrayil, Zangilan, Gubadli, Aghdam, Kalbajar, Lachin, Khojavend, Khojaly, and Shusha; production of gold products and livestock in the districts of Kalbajar and Zangilan; copper mining in the Zangilan district; silver and mercury production in the districts of Kalbajar and Lachin; development logistics and establishment all necessary facilities in this regard in the Eastern Zangesur as well as in other regions; tourism facilities in Shusha, Kalbecer, Zengilan; development of Higher education schools and research institutes in the liberated regions; development of wind and solar energy; innovative development of agriculture; development of medical centers and sanatoriums; development of the textile industry.

Conclusion: The liberated territories of Azerbaijan are rich in natural resources and the efficient use of these resources can allow Azerbaijan's economy to develop more rapidly. Organizing and developing entrepreneurship in these areas is one of the most important methods to make it through this potential. It is believed that the creation of new and modern business entities in the liberated territories, will contribute to the achievement of the following organizational, technical, and socio-economic advantages: effective use of resources; create ideal conditions for the use of new technology, new equipment, and ICT; implementation of specific innovation projects in collaboration; expansion of financial opportunities and export potential; opportunities in the regions for organizing foreign and joint ventures, clusters, regional business associations, financial and industrial groups, business incubators, start-ups, and development in logistics. Development in the logistics sector will improve international trade, boosts country competitiveness, and so appears to be a significant predictor of growth and development.

All within the framework of international law, Azerbaijan must make Armenia take an official obligation to compensate for the damage caused by the Republic of Armenia, as well as force Armenia to recognize Azerbaijan's territorial integrity and sign a peace agreement as well as provide the opening of the Zangazur corridor.

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